

Illicit antiques trade network

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Illicit antiques trade network project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Daria Stefan will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	generated_labels.csv	Plain text	text/plain	100 - 1000 MB	no
P2	umap_embeddings.npy		application/octet-stream	100 - 1000 MB	no
P3	similar_entities_Giacomo_Medici.json	Plain text	text/plain	100 - 1000 MB	no
P4	entity_embeddings.npy		application/octet-stream	100 - 1000 MB	no
P5	cosine_similarity_matrix.npy		application/octet-stream	100 - 1000 MB	no
P6	results_TransE.json	Plain text	text/plain	100 - 1000 MB	no
P7	model_TransE.pt	Archived data	application/zip	100 - 1000 MB	no
P8	resultsDistMult.json	Plain text	text/plain	100 - 1000 MB	no
P9	modelDistMult.pt	Archived data	application/zip	100 - 1000 MB	no
P10	resultsConvE.json	Plain text	text/plain	100 - 1000 MB	no
P11	resultsComplex.json	Plain text	text/plain	100 - 1000 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P12	modelConvE.pt	Archived data	application/zip	100 - 1000 MB	no
P13	modelComplex.pt	Archived data	application/zip	100 - 1000 MB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	A knowledge graph of an illicit trading network	https://zenodo.org/records/7785908	CC-BY-4.0 The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited.	no

Description for "A knowledge graph of an illicit trading network":

RDF Triples representing the relationship between people, institutions, countries and the movement of archaeological material. Collected by Graham et al.

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The initial data for this project is drawn from an existing domain dataset (55.6 KiB), in .csv format, representing statements about the flow of material and interpersonal relationships in an illicit artifact and antiques trade network, following the RDF structure ("head", "relationship", "tail"). This dataset contains 477 unique entities and 1,204 relationships.

The input data created for this project consists of a modification of the original .csv dataset with all special characters removed (55.6 KiB), a histogram of all types of relationships (100KiB, PNG), a plot of the knowledge graph resulting from the modified .csv (258.7 KiB, PNG).

The knowledge graph is stored and managed in Neo4j. Access to the graph database is provided via the Neo4j Bolt protocol (bolt://localhost:7687). Connection credentials (username and password) are handled securely using a .env file rather than hardcoded values. The initial dataset is uploaded as a pandas Dataframe and the corresponding nodes and relationships are created in Neo4j using Cypher queries.

A structured metadata record capturing the number of nodes and edges, the list of node identifiers, the types of relationships, and a unique dataset identifier with a timestamp is generated every time graph data is fetched from the database. This metadata is saved in JSON format and stored in a designated log directory, making each dataset snapshot findable, identifiable, and reusable. The resulting files form a verifiable audit trail of data generation, which facilitates reproducibility of experiments for downstream machine learning tasks.

Entity-label associations are automatically generated using the spaCy library, saved as a .csv and uploaded to the database.

Four PyKeen embedding models - transE, complexE and distMult - are trained, validated and tested, using a standard pipeline and evaluator. For each model, the trained model's weights are saved in PyTorch format (.pt), while its training configuration and evaluation metrics are stored as JSON files. Chosen metrics, including rank metrics and hits@K are plotted for all four models. The plots are saved as .png files under descriptive names which correspond to the content of each plot. A dedicated directory is created automatically, ensuring consistency and minimizing manual intervention.

The entity embeddings of the best ranking model are extracted, reduced to 2D using UMAP, and used to compute a cosine similarity matrix, enabling identification of the top-N most similar entities to the given entity. The extracted entity embeddings, their 2D UMAP projections, and the cosine similarity matrix are saved in NumPy binary format (.npy), while the top-N similar entities are converted to native Python types and stored as a JSON file. The UMAP projection is plotted and saved as .png in the dedicated directory.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Students and general public

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention. Version control is automate with GitHub.

Persistent DOIs have been assigned to the entire project, the input dataset, and the train, validation, and test splits via the Database Repository, ensuring that the data are publicly accessible (DOI: 10.82556/xfvk-2712). Additionally, all research outputs, including the computational notebook used for data processing and analysis, have been archived in TUWRD and are available under DOI 10.70124/ccmqc-e2c74. Full citation details for the associated research article are also provided to ensure transparency regarding data provenance. All materials are released under a CC-BY 4.0 license, allowing for broad reuse and redistribution with appropriate attribution. . This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P2	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P5	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P6	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P7	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P8	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P9	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P10	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P11	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P12	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P13	Open		2025-03-05	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR

principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The datasets are provided in standard formats such as CSV, which can be accessed with common data analysis tools including Microsoft Excel, LibreOffice, or any programming environment that supports CSV file handling, such as Python or R. For full reuse, especially for tasks like model training or evaluation, users will benefit from having Python installed along with libraries such as pandas, PyTorch, and PyKEEN. The computational notebook, shared in Jupyter Notebook format (.ipynb), also requires a Jupyter environment to open and run. All software required is open-source and freely available, ensuring that users without access to proprietary tools can still fully interact with the data.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and reuse within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

To ensure interoperability and facilitate data exchange and reuse, the project follows widely accepted standards and formats. The datasets are provided in CSV format, a simple and machine-readable standard that is compatible across disciplines and platforms. Community-endorsed best practices, such as using human-readable labels for entities and relationships instead of internal identifiers, are implemented to improve understanding across different domains. While no uncommon or project-specific ontologies were necessary, entity and relationship labels are consistent with the terminology used in the Trafficking Culture Project Encyclopedia, and mappings to broader criminological and cultural heritage vocabularies could be developed if needed in future work.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

To ensure data validation and facilitate reuse, we will provide comprehensive documentation for all published datasets, including detailed README files that explain the methodology, data cleaning procedures, variable definitions, units of measurement, and software requirements. Each dataset will also include metadata describing the structure, provenance, and processing steps, and will cite the associated research article to maintain full traceability. All datasets and related outputs will be made openly available in the public domain through trusted repositories (DBRepo and TUWRD) under a Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license, ensuring the widest possible reuse without restrictions, in line with Grant Agreement obligations. The data will remain accessible and usable by third parties beyond.

The following data quality checks will be done: repeated samples or measurements and peer review of data.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

This project will also generate digital research outputs, including computational notebooks, data processing scripts, trained machine learning models, and visualizations (e.g., knowledge graph plots and relationship histograms). These outputs will be managed and shared according to the same FAIR principles applied to the datasets. All scripts and notebooks will be made openly available through the

TUWRD repository, with persistent DOIs assigned, clear versioning, and licensing under CC BY 4.0 to ensure transparency and reusability. Metadata accompanying these outputs will describe the software environments, dependencies, and usage instructions, enabling third parties to reproduce or adapt the workflows. Where applicable, models will be shared in standard formats (e.g., PyTorch checkpoints) along with documentation describing their training parameters and evaluation results. By providing these additional research outputs with full documentation, open licensing, and permanent accessibility, the project ensures that not only the data, but also the processes and models developed, remain reusable and interoperable for future research across disciplines.

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Coordinator (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will not be stored on TU Wien servers. For long-term preservation and public access, all datasets, code, and research outputs have been deposited in trusted external repositories (DBRepo and TUWRD), which ensure safe storage, professional curation, and persistent access through assigned DOIs.

P1 (generated_labels.csv), R1 (A knowledge graph of an illicit trading network), P2 (umap_embeddings.npy), P3 (similar_entities_Giacomo_Medici.json), P4 (entity_embeddings.npy), P5 (cosine_similarity_matrix.npy), P6 (results_TransE.json), P7 (model_TransE.pt), P8 (resultsDistMult.json), P9 (modelDistMult.pt), P10 (resultsConvE.json), P11 (resultsCompEx.json), P12 (modelConvE.pt), P13 (modelCompEx.pt) will be stored on GitHub. External storage will be used because institutional storage will not be used because the datasets and related materials have been deposited in established external repositories (database repository and tuwrd) that provide persistent identifiers (dois), public accessibility, and long-term preservation. these repositories are specifically designed to ensure data findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (fair principles) at a level that institutional storage alone may not guarantee. additionally, using dedicated repositories allows for broader visibility and easier citation within the research community, while institutional storage is typically intended for internal use and may not offer the same degree of public access or metadata integration.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
P5	writing	writing	reading only
P6	writing	writing	reading only
P7	writing	writing	reading only
P8	writing	writing	reading only
P9	writing	writing	reading only
P10	writing	writing	reading only
P11	writing	writing	reading only

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P12	writing	writing	reading only
P13	writing	writing	reading only
R1	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P4	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P5	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P6	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P7	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P8	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P9	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P10	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P11	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P12	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P13	TU Wien Research Data	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

Information regarding rights and control of access to data has yet to be identified.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise. The research plan of the project was reviewed by an ethics committee / the TU Wien Research Ethics Committee / a similar body.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?